

Smoking: Does Personality Trait Play Any Significant Role?Nandini Lahoty¹, Maninder Kaur², Tuhina Sharma³, Bhuwan Sharma⁴¹MA Student, Department of Psychology, University of Delhi, New Delhi²Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, PIMS Medical College, Jalandhar³Senior Consultant, Infosys Consulting, Pune⁴Professor, Department of Community Medicine, PIMS Medical College, Jalandhar

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Abstract:

Introduction: Tobacco smoking is the reason for killing 8 million people every year with the greatest burden on low- and middle-income countries. Studies have reported the relation between smoking and personality traits. In present study, we aimed to evaluate the differences in personalities of smokers and non-smokers in the rural area of Rajasthan.

Materials & Methods: Study included 80 adolescents and adult subjects, of which 40 each were smokers and non-smokers. The personality assessment of the subjects were done through NEO-FFI (Costa & McCrae, 1992). Collected data was imported from Excel sheets to SPSS software ver. 26.0.

Results: Neuroticism trait was significantly associated with smokers (67.5% vs 35%) while non-smoking behavior was associated with Conscientiousness ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Present study found a notable correlation between neuroticism and the habit of smoking while conscientiousness seems to act as a protective factor against the progression and continuation of smoking. Thus, specific personality traits, particularly neuroticism, should be evaluated and potentially addressed in intervention programs targeting smoking behaviour.

Keywords: Addiction, Neuroticism, Personality Type, Rural area, Smoking.

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Introduction

Tobacco smoking has been a health hazard for decades. It is the reason for killing 8 million people every year, including 1.3 million non-smokers who are exposed to passive smoking [1]. The burden of tobacco consumption is highest in low- and middle-income countries. Global Adult tobacco survey (2008-2010) provides comprehensive information about tobacco consumption in 14 low- and middle-income countries, including the United States and United Kingdom. The study found 852 million tobacco smokers in these 16 countries alone, with China leading in the number of smokers, followed by India; 274.9 million [2]. The initiation of tobacco consumption usually starts in childhood or adolescence, that is usually between the age of 10-19 years [3]. The usage of tobacco is generally higher in males which is, 1 in every 5 boys between the age 13-15 years [4]. The early consumption of tobacco products aggravates nicotine dependence in adulthood and leads to the vicious cycle of smoking throughout one's life [5,6]. In India, the Global Youth Tobacco Survey 2019 revealed that 8.5% of students, that is a total of 9.6% boys and 7.5% girls, between the ages 13-15 are engaged in tobacco consumption. 11% and 21% of students are

exposed to second-hand smoke at home and enclosed public places, respectively [7]. The GYTS-4 report further highlights that 10.6 % of tobacco smokers quit smoking in the past year and 20.6% of smokers wanted to quit smoking tobacco. Smoking cessation depends upon many factors, one of them being personality traits [8]. Personality, as an accumulation of traits have been operationalised by Costa and McCrae in the Five Factor Model. These traits are relatively stable across situations and are the building blocks of behaviour [9]. The FFM is a hierarchical model that classifies traits into 5 factors. Neuroticism, the tendency to experience negative emotions and inclination towards fear; Extraversion, is the tendency to be assertive and social, instead of being quiet or reserved; Openness to experience is characterised by emotional sensitivity, creativity and intellect. Agreeableness involves truthfulness, cooperation, altruism, and lastly Conscientiousness involves characteristics of strong will, determination, organised, task-focused [10, 11]. To a certain extent, these traits are heritable [12] and generalisable across cultures [13]. The relation between smoking and personality traits was first

observed by Eysenk in 1983. Earlier studies reported a relationship between smoking and extraversion, claiming that current smokers exhibited higher extraversion than non-smokers [14]. Another study conducted in Poland revealed that smokers are more Extraverted than non-smokers. Facet analysis of the Big 5 traits reported that current smokers' activity and excitement seeking (facets of extraversion) scores were higher relative to those of never and former smokers. Even though there was no significant difference between smokers and non-smokers on Conscientiousness, the dutifulness and deliberation (facets of conscientiousness) scores of smokers were lower compared with those who never smoked or formerly smoked [15]. Moreover, extraversion has a significant positive effect on transitioning from a lower to higher stages of cigarette and hookah smoker [16]. Meanwhile, other studies reported a relationship between smoking and other Big Five Personality traits. People who smoked were high on neuroticism and comparatively low on agreeableness and conscientiousness from non-smokers [17,18]. A 10-year study among US adults revealed that personality traits such as high openness to experience and high neuroticism is associated with the risk of lifetime cigarette use. Furthermore, Neuroticism can progress an occasional smoker to persistent daily smoker [19]. Maternal Smoking during pregnancy has also revealed effects on the personality of their offsprings [20]. High levels of Neuroticism, Extraversion and lower levels of Conscientiousness were observed in the offspring of mothers who smoked during their pregnancy, relative to those who did not smoke. The prevalence of tobacco smoking has shown significant differences in varied geographical regions of the country, for example, at the village level, district and city level respectively [21]. Studies have highlighted that the prevalence of tobacco smoking is highest at rural level [22,23]. The present study was thus conducted to assess the differences in personalities

of smokers and non-smokers in the rural area of Rajasthan, Rawatbhata.

Materials and Methods

Present cross-sectional study was conducted at a semi-rural area, Rawatbhata in Rajasthan, India during the period of May to June 2024. Study included 80 adolescents and adult subjects (>10 years) who gave written informed consent to participate in the study.

Among the 80 participants, 40 were smokers (smoking for a minimum of 2 years) and 40 were non-smokers. Individuals who were engaged in any other means of substance except smoking and subjects with major psychiatric disorders that could influence smoking behaviour were excluded from the study. Control population included subjects with no history of smoking or occasional smoking.

The personality assessment of the subjects were done through NEO-FFI (Costa & McCrae, 1992), which is a self-report questionnaire consisting of 60 items answered on a 5 point Likert Scale ranging from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree. The NEO-FFI is a shorter version of NEO-PI (Personality Inventory), which assesses 30 facets, six for each dimension in the FFM (Neuroticism, Extraversion, Openness, Agreeableness and Conscientiousness). Normative data are used to standardise raw scores into T-scores (M=50, SD=10). NEO-FFI scale has shown longitudinal stability, cross-observer agreement, and convergent and discriminant validity in a large body of studies (Costa & McCrae 1992) [24,25]. Collected data was imported from Excel sheets to SPSS software ver. 26.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA) for analysis. Qualitative data was compared using fisher exact test while quantitative data (i.e. scoring) was compared using Man Whitney U-test between the groups. Spearman correlation analysis was used to compute correlation between personality scores and other variables. A p-value of < 0.05 was taken as level of significance.

Results

Table 1: Distribution of patients according to joint involvement

Variable		N	Group				p-value
			Non-Smoker (n=40)		Smoker (n=40)		
Age (yrs)	Meas +/- SD		26.20	5.28	27.10	4.95	0.43
BMI (Kg/m ²)	Meas +/- SD		23.17	2.16	23.79	3.02	0.59
Gender	Female	25	15	37.5%	10	25.0%	0.35
	Male	55	25	62.5%	30	75.0%	
SES	Lower	15	6	15.0%	9	22.5%	0.77
	Middle	52	27	67.5%	25	62.5%	
	Upper	13	7	17.5%	6	15.0%	
Personality Type	Agreeableness	1	0	0.0%	1	2.5%	0.027
	Conscientiousness	22	15	37.5%	7	17.5%	
	Extraversion	9	7	17.5%	2	5.0%	
	Neuroticism	41	14	35.0%	27	67.5%	

	Openness	7	4	10.0%	3	7.5%	
				0.0%		0.0%	
Personality Scores (Mean +/- SD)	Agreeableness		26.18	4.24	25.43	4.40	0.78
	Conscientiousness		34.53	4.26	31.28	5.74	<0.01
	Extraversion		26.03	5.84	23.20	4.78	0.02
	Neuroticism		21.03	6.05	26.43	5.13	<0.01
	Openness		24.10	4.78	23.08	4.68	0.48

Table 2: Correlation analysis of Neuroticism Score with age, BMI and duration of smoking

Spearman co-relation		
Neuroticism Score	r- value	p- value
Age (yrs)	-0.187	0.097
BMI (Kg/m ²)	-0.156	0.212
Duration of Smoking (yrs)	0.078	0.634

The mean age of smokers and non-smokers was 27.1 years and 26.2 years with male predominance in both groups. Both the groups were comparable with regards to baseline demographic data and body mass index (Table 1). On evaluating the personality types between smokers and non-smokers, we observed that Neuroticism trait was significantly associated with smokers (67.5% vs 35%) while non-smoking behavior was associated with Conscientiousness ($p < 0.05$). On Correlation analysis, we observed no significant correlation between Neuroticism Score with age, BMI and duration of smoking ($p > 0.05$) (Table 2).

Discussion

The results of the present study revealed that smokers scored significantly higher in neuroticism (67.5%), as compared to non-smokers (35%). The result aligned with other studies claiming that individuals high on neuroticism often indulge in cigarette smoking [17,18,19]. However, no correlation was reported between Neuroticism score and age, duration of smoking or BMI. This observation suggests that individuals with high levels of neuroticism- tendency to experience distress, dissatisfaction, anxiousness, tension and irritability- are more likely to engage in cigarette smoking. Importantly, neuroticism does not seem to be influenced by the duration of smoking, age of the individual or BMI. Thus, neuroticism seems to be a significant predictor of smoking behaviour, independent of these other factors.

Studies have also reported that neuroticism is significantly associated with increased risk of lifetime cigarette use [26]. Another study [27] has shown that neuroticism is an independent predictor of smoking. In simpler terms, every one point increase in neuroticism, co-occurring panic and cigarette smoking increases four-fold. Furthermore, neuroticism is considered to be a factor that maintains smoking and changes an occasional smoker to a persistent, daily smoker [19]. These findings suggest initial evidence that neuroticism might indicate a common underlying vulnerability

to both cigarette smoking and panic attacks occurring together.

Cigarette smoking has been used as a coping mechanism by people under stressful situations [28]. As a means to cope with the stressful situation, individuals with high neuroticism are more likely to turn to destructive habits, such as smoking [29]. This might be one of the reasons why individuals with high neuroticism engage in cigarette smoking. Studies have suggested that neuroticism also makes the individual impulsive. Impulsivity further leads to indulging in risky behaviour such as smoking [30] and vice-versa.

An unusual finding is identified in the present study. The mean score of Extraversion is significantly higher in Non-Smokers than Smokers. Earlier studies have reported otherwise [14-16]. Studies have underscored that a high level of extraversion leads to high-risky behaviour such as smoking. Extroverts are driven by their inclination towards excitement seeking and social interactions which further engage them in smoking behaviour [16]. Another study has reported differences in smoking between introverts and extraverts. Introverts usually smoke under stressful situations to attain tranquilization, whereas extraverts smoke during low arousal situations [31]. Other studies report no significant association between extraversion and smoking [8, 18].

However, the present study has reported that non-smokers are more extraverted ($M=26.03$) as compared to smokers ($M=23.20$). Reasons for the same could include the 'social stigma' surrounding smoking behaviour which might lead to the smoker's isolation. Secondly, since studies have confirmed that smoking is used as a coping mechanism [28,29], people might not contact their immediate social circle when faced with stress.

They would rather rely on cigarette smoking than getting help from the outside. This could lead to more extraversion in non-smokers as compared to smokers. Lastly, the relationship between substance-use and personality traits is complex.

More extraverted individuals might prefer other stimulating activities over smoking, whereas introverts would use smoking for calmness.

Lastly, the present study found conscientiousness of non-smokers ($M=34.53$) as significantly higher than smokers ($M=31.28$). Prior studies have also reported that smokers have low conscientiousness, as compared to non-smokers [17,18,20]. Low conscientiousness is significantly associated with poor health habits such as smoking [32]. Conscientiousness- the tendency to be goal-directed, self-disciplined, impulse-control and cautious- has a protective effect against smoking [33]. A 24-year follow up study from the Czech Republic indicated that low conscientiousness in childhood led to smoking in adulthood [34]. Therefore, the present study aligns with the prior work highlighting that high conscientiousness safeguards an individual against smoking cigarettes.

Other than the traits Neuroticism, Extraversion and Conscientiousness, there were no significant differences between the scores of smokers and non-smokers.

Conclusion

Neuroticism is a personality trait that is classified as one of the five higher-order factors in the Five-Factor Model. Individuals with elevated levels of neuroticism frequently experience anxiety and tension. This study found a notable correlation between neuroticism and the habit of smoking. The results of our study indicate that neuroticism may have a role in both the initiation of cigarette usage and the advancement of smoking. Additionally, conscientiousness seems to act as a protective factor against the progression and continuation of smoking. This result contributes to an expanding body of research indicating that specific personality traits, particularly neuroticism, should be evaluated and potentially addressed in intervention programs targeting smoking behaviour.

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